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BIOARCHAEOLOGY IN THE EASTERN MEDITERRANEAN AND MIDDLE EAST: ARE WE AS RELEVANT AS WE SHOULD BE? ADDRESSING CLIMATE CHANGE, MIGRATION, INTERSECTIONALITY AND VIOLENCE

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ABSTRACT

The Eastern Mediterranean and Middle East (EMME) has been the setting of significant societal and cultural changes over millennia, and served as a connecting point for cultures across Asia, Europe, and Africa. Bioarchaeology, the contextual study of past human remains, explores the dynamic relationship between and within biological, natural, environmental, socio-political, historical, and physical forces; as such, it has found important applications in the EMME. This paper briefly outlines the history of bioarchaeological research in the region and highlights contemporary themes and trends. The latter follow the research trends in Europe and North America with a focus on palaeopathology, followed by dietary reconstructions, activity patterns, and mobility. Emphasis is placed on the extent to which bioarchaeology in the EMME has adopted the concept of intersectionality, which is especially pertinent in the region, but also the degree to which it has explored key issues with contemporary significance, such as migration, structural violence, and climate change. The above concepts and topics can indeed be identified in EMME bioarchaeological studies over the past few years; however, intersectionality and structural violence are almost exclusively addressed implicitly, while all four themes should receive more attention in the future so that they enhance the understanding of these processes in the EMME with greater spatial and temporal resolution.

KEYWORDS: Eastern Mediterranean, Human Skeletal Remains, Middle East, Research Trends, Intersectionality, Climate Change, Violence, Migration

1. INTRODUCTION

Bioarchaeology focuses on the study of human remains from archaeological contexts. Given the complex biocultural nature of humans, bioarchaeology explores the dynamic relationship between and within diverse biological, natural, environmental, socio-political, historical, and physical forces (Baker and Agarwal, 2017; Buikstra et al., 2022; Nikita and Chovalopoulou, 2023). The Eastern Mediterranean and Middle East (EMME), geographically situated at the crossroads of three continents (Fig. 1), has gone through and is still experiencing major ecological, socio-cultural, and political transformations, and it has served as a melting pot for diverse civilizations throughout human history (Perry, 2012a). As such, bioarchaeology in the EMME could find very important applications.

Many reviews have examined the evolution of bioarchaeological research in different EMME regions, discussing the research questions it has addressed, the challenges it has faced, and what the future may hold. For the Arabian Peninsula, Martin (2007) focused on bioarchaeology in the United Arab Emirates, whereas Frohlich et al. (1989) explored the progress of palaeopathology in Bahrain. These reviews emphasized the small number of studies of human behavior and biological adaptation in Eastern Arabia, a region considered marginal to the larger cultural centers of the Eastern Mediterranean. The state of bioarchaeological research in Cyprus has been addressed in a review by Harper and Fox (2008). This review examined key themes that have been studied in different periods, it discussed the problems associated with conducting bioarchaeological research in Cyprus (such as poor preservation, commingled skeletal assemblages, and historical bias) and emphasized the need to establish bioarchaeology programs at local universities and institutions, as most Cypriot bioarchaeologists are trained abroad before entering the job market in the island. A recent review by Ioannou and Lorentz (2022) provides an updated account of the developments in Cypriot bioarchaeology. The paper highlights the notable shift towards a more scientific approach in the late twentieth century, which has led to significant advancements in the field of bioarchaeology. Specifically, there has been a marked increase in problem-oriented studies that address bioarchaeological questions, and researchers have increasingly employed scientific techniques beyond the traditional morphological and metric approaches. Moreover, the proper excavation, recording, and recovery of human remains have improved significantly, and interdisciplinary approaches have become more prevalent, leading to an overall improvement in the state of bio-

archaeological research in Cyprus in recent years. Bioarchaeological reviews on Egypt have addressed certain research themes, such as palaeopathology and biodistances (Keita, 1993; Metcalfe et al., 2014), though in a review of bioarchaeology in the Nile River and the Levant several research themes and their popularity across time have been explored, as well as methodological and theoretical advances (Rose, 2017). These reviews highlighted the role of technological advancements and scientific developments in incorporating Egyptian bioarchaeology within wider scientific and historical debates such as the evolution of humans, cultures, and diseases. They also discussed the promising developments in Egyptian bioarchaeology and how new analytical methods are challenging preconceived notions about certain topics, such as Egyptian biological transitions and genetic origins. In the Levant, an extensive review by Sheridan (2017) delved into the state of research in the region and how it may be integrated within a more holistic bioarchaeological model, whereas a more focused review for palaeopathology for the same region was written by Perry (2012b), highlighting the lack of integration among diverse but interconnected aspects of bioarchaeology and standard methods for collecting skeletal data, as well as parameters that limit comparative research, such as poorly presented data and sampling biases. More recently, Nikita and Triantaphyllou (2017) reviewed the bioarchaeological developments in Greece and how research trends adapted to the standards established in the United States and United Kingdom after a long tradition of research following a physical anthropological approach, while a short report by Sołtysiak (2006) discussed the progress in human skeletal studies for Iraq in the years 2001 and 2002. Finally, mention should be made to the edited volume by Porter and Boutin (2014) which, although not a review work, presents through the contributions of researchers with different backgrounds, the diverse ways in which various regions in the ancient Near East commemorated their dead, integrating mortuary with bioarchaeological analysis.

The above papers collectively show that despite practical, methodological and conceptual limitations, the contextualized analysis of human remains from the EMME region can yield important temporal and spatial information about health, activity, disease, diet, mobility, and other parameters of past life. In this paper, we explore trends of bioarchaeological research in the EMME during 2015-2021, and the extent to which the research themes mostly developed in the region have been employed to assess issues of contemporary relevance, such as migration, violence, climate change and intersectionality.

Figure 1. Map of the EMME region including names and borders of modern nation-states, compiled in QGIS using open-source shapefiles (<https://www.naturalearthdata.com/downloads/10m-raster-data/> and <https://www.naturalearthdata.com/downloads/10m-cultural-vectors/>)

2. BRIEF HISTORY AND CURRENT TRENDS OF BIOARCHAEOLOGY IN THE EMME

2.1. *The early years*

Bioarchaeology in the EMME has a long tradition. Studies in the early twentieth century were largely individualistic, descriptive, and typological, frequently overlooking the synthesis of biological, archaeological, and historical narratives. These studies mostly focused on metric data to explore morphological variation, which was viewed as indicating racial differences (Henckel, 1930; Kansu, 1930; Woo, 1930). Still, even at that early stage, there were bioarchaeological studies focused on context-specific investigations from various regions and time periods, involving different parameters such as demography, diet, and pathology (Kansu and Tunakan, 1946; Krogman, 1940; Netolitzky, 1943). It is during the 1970s that bioarchaeology gradually developed into a distinct discipline characterized by the integration of biological, environmental, social, and cultural parameters that shape the human skeleton. A more synergistic and holistic approach was promoted to answer research

questions based on quantifiable data, material culture, and modern archaeological/social history (Buikstra, 1977). In the EMME region these trends are exemplified in the work on ancient population dynamics and health by J. Lawrence Angel, focused mainly on Greece, Cyprus and Turkey, with marginal emphasis on Egypt (e.g. Angel, 1970, 1972, 1975, 1977, 1979, 1980). Similarly, bioarchaeological research in the Arabian Peninsula by Peter Cornwall in the 1940s and Karen Højgaard in the 1980s established a foundational understanding for the human assemblages excavated in this region (e.g., Cornwall, 1943, 1944, 1946; Højgaard, 1980, 1981, 1983, 1984, 1985, 1986).

2.2. *Current research trends*

Recent decades have witnessed a surge in the number of bioarchaeological research globally and in the EMME (Nikita et al., 2021). In this paper we focus on the most recent trends, that is, studies published from 2015 to 2021 at international journals in bioarchaeology, physical anthropology, archaeological science, anthropological archaeology and palaeopathology, as well as at regional journals with thematic linked to bioarchaeology, anthropology and archaeological sciences, but also in books as chapters or appendices,

and as graduate theses or professional reports (for details see Nikita et al. 2021).

The distribution of publications by theme (Figure 2) showed that palaeopathology has been the most systematically examined topic, followed by diet and then mobility and activity-related skeletal changes. These trends show an overall similar pattern to earlier periods (Nikita et al., 2021), supporting broadly a continuity in the interest for specific biocultural parameters over others. We must note that the other topics examined by Nikita et al. (2021) included ancient DNA, biodistance, demography, isotopes, metrics, nonmetrics, stature, and taphonomy. Among these, ancient DNA, biodistance, isotopes, metrics, and nonmetrics have not been included in the current paper because they do not represent research themes themselves but methods/approaches to examine diet, mobility, or other aspects of past life; thus, only papers that used these methods to address diet and mobility have been included in the current paper under one of these two themes. Demography, which is a very common theme in bioarchaeological research, is not discussed here because, as Nikita et al. (2021) highlight, they have included in this category all papers with any mention of sex or age-at-death data, while actual palaeodemographic studies were extremely rare. Finally, taphonomy is usually studied to examine the preservation of the remains, thus the extent to which they can furnish accurate interpretations for past populations; hence, it is mostly a preliminary step of other bioarchaeological analyses focused on one of the other themes (e.g. pathology, diet, mobility).

In the following sections, we offer a brief presentation of the basic principles of each theme of skeletal analysis with a few representative examples from the EMME that cover different methods, time periods and regions.

2.2.1. Palaeopathology

Palaeopathology is the study of past disease processes. It is based on the fact that the human skeleton, as a living tissue, tends to respond to pathological insults via new bone formation, bone resorption, abnormal bone size and/or abnormal bone shape (Ortner, 2003). In addition to the fact that most pathological conditions do not affect the skeleton, a major challenge in palaeopathology is the identification of diseases given that the skeleton responds to multiple pathological agents in a similar manner. Therefore, many different pathological conditions will manifest very similarly and differential diagnosis is difficult or even impossible in many cases (Buikstra et al., 2019). Another important complication is interpretational and is captured under the 'osteological paradox'. Because individuals with skeletal lesions were able to

survive the stressful conditions that led to the formation of these lesions, the osteological paradox suggests that skeletal lesions could actually indicate greater resilience (e.g. less frailty) (Wood et al., 1992). Other important aspects of the osteological paradox are *hidden heterogeneity*, which refers to the unequal vulnerability of individuals to diseases and stressors, and the risks of death they face; and *selective mortality*, which relates to the fact that palaeopathological assemblages represent the dead, thus, they are biased representatives of the once-living population (Wood et al., 1992).

Regardless of these limitations, palaeopathological research holds a central place in bioarchaeology and is among the most commonly explored topics globally. Palaeopathological research in the EMME has focused on diseases with different etiology and employed different analytical methods. For instance, studies in this region have examined infectious (Tomczyk, 2013), metabolic (Pitre et al., 2016), neoplastic (Khwaileh, 2016) and joint (Karligkioti et al., 2022) diseases, as well as trauma (Bourbou, 2003), among others. The methods used to identify the above diseases have been macroscopic but also microscopic (e.g. palaeoparasitology - Anastasiou et al., 2018), molecular (ancient DNA - Hershkovitz et al., 2008) and radiographic (Bourke, 1967). Some of the palaeopathological studies had a methodological focus, stressing the potential and limitations of differential diagnosis (e.g. Khwaileh, 2016; Tomczyk, 2013), while others have emphasized the interpretation of the pathological lesions in the context of diet and cultural behaviors (e.g. Bourbou, 2003; Karligkioti et al., 2022; Pitre et al., 2016).

2.2.2. Diet

Different bioarchaeological proxies may be used to study the diet of past populations. Non-destructive methods rely on dental disease and dental wear patterns, while destructive methods include stable isotope and dental calculus microdebris analysis. Dental diseases and dental wear patterns offer an indirect approach to reconstructing subsistence practices and dietary habits by pointing to the relative consumption of carbohydrates and proteins, as well as food processing strategies (e.g. food softening, removal/addition of inclusions) (Forshaw, 2014). Stable isotopes, especially of carbon and nitrogen, in human bone and teeth reveal details about dietary patterns and food intake (Makarewicz and Sealy, 2015). Using such isotopes, a diet may be classified as high or low in animal-derived protein, high or low in C3 (such as legumes, cereals) or C4 (such as millet, maize) plants, or as fish-based or not. Finally, the micro-excavation of dental calculus deposits may identify starches, phyto-

liths and other particles originating from consumption practices, though the calculus matrix also entraps microparticles that have entered the mouth accidentally through inhalation or the use of the teeth as tools (Radini et al., 2017).

In the EMME, palaeodietary studies have employed macroscopic, microscopic and isotopic approaches. The research questions have varied, including, among others, sex differences in dietary patterns (Vergidou et al., 2021), diachronic dietary change (Afshar et al., 2019), diet and animal management practices (Scirè-Calabrisotto et al., 2020), as well as subsistence strategies (Al-Bashaireh and Al-Muheisen, 2011).

2.2.3. Mobility

Past mobility may be explored via biodistance, isotopic and ancient DNA analysis. Biological distance or biodistance is a measure of biological affinity (or divergence) between and within human groups, based on skeletal and dental phenotypic variation (Mardini et al., 2023; Nikita et al., 2019; Pilloud and Larsen, 2011). Biodistance analysis is based on the premise that skeletal and dental shape and size are partly heritable, thus the phenotype can be used as a proxy for the genotype (Rathmann and Reyes-Centeno, 2020). Since biological affinities identified at an inter- and intra-regional scale may be interpreted as the result of gene flow (the movement of individuals and the genetic material they carry from one group to another), biodistances offer insights to past mobility patterns (Pilloud and Hefner, 2016). Past mobility may also be examined via isotopic analysis, especially combining strontium and oxygen isotopes. Comparing these isotope values between the teeth of past individuals and the so-called baseline in the area where these individuals were found, suggests whether the individuals were 'local' or 'non-local' (Bentley, 2006; Pederzani and Britton, 2019). A limitation of this approach is that it cannot securely identify the point of origin of the 'non-locals'. To address this issue, there

has been an increasing number of studies establishing bioavailable baselines and isoscapes across the world (Blank et al., 2018; Reynaga et al., 2021) and in the EMME more specifically (Dotsika et al., 2018; Ladegaard-Pedersen et al., 2020). Finally, ancient DNA (aDNA) analysis investigates human migration by identifying the past and present populations with whom archaeological individuals under study are genetically most similar (Bongers et al., 2020; Gao et al., 2015).

Mobility studies in the EMME have adopted biodistances, isotopic and ancient DNA analyses to explore various topics, such as the association between mobility and economic change (Afshar, 2014), residential mobility (Buzon and Simonetti, 2013), social endogamy (Alt et al., 2013), the presence of pilgrims (Wong et al. 2018), mobility as a response to climate change (Gregoricka, 2016), population dynamics during the European Neolithic expansion (Silva et al., 2022) and others.

2.2.4. Activity

Physical and mechanical stress due to manual labor may result in activity-related skeletal changes, such as osteoarthritis, Schmorl's nodes, enthesal changes, and enhanced biomechanical properties (Schrader, 2019). Although the exact nature of the physical activities in which past individuals engaged is impossible to securely assess exclusively via skeletal evidence (Jurmain et al., 2011), the examination of the above-mentioned skeletal changes can help make inferences on broad past patterns of manual labor (e.g. Eng, 2016; Nikita et al., 2011; Üstündağ, 2009).

Such skeletal changes have also been utilized in the EMME to assess gender-related labor division in different groups (Üstündağ, 2020), or among individuals with different social status to examine how labor may be divided based on social stratification (Refai, 2019), as well as between different assemblages to explore chronological and regional differences in occupational stress (Karligkioti et al., 2022).

Figure 2. Number of papers published during 2015-2021 sorted by key theme and region. Data retrieved from Bi(bli)oArch (Nikita et al., 2021).

The above themes –pathology, mobility, diet, activity- represent topics commonly addressed in the international bioarchaeological literature. Some of these themes are also strongly linked with pressing contemporary issues. For example, these themes could be examined in the context of addressing questions such as: How did climate change affect health and disease (pathology), mobility patterns (migration or other forms of movement), diet and occupational patterns (activity)? What forms did violence take in the past (e.g. physical violence manifesting as trauma (pathology) and/or structural violence taking the form of unequal access to dietary resources, labor division (activity) disadvantaging certain groups, physiological stress (pathology), among other forms of violence)? How did mobility affect dietary preferences and exposure to diseases? The following section examines the degree to which the themes of pathology, mobility, diet and activity have actually been explored within such broader pressing research topics in the EMME.

3. ADDRESSING CONTEMPORARY ISSUES IN THE EMME

The EMME region has witnessed complex economic, social and political changes and transitions throughout its history. As bioarchaeology serves to interpret human remains within their biological, sociocultural, historical, and environmental framework, it can offer a deep time perspective to pressing contem-

porary issues and contribute towards a better understanding of the diachronic effects of climate change, human mobility, and violence, among many other important processes (Agarwal and Glencross, 2011). A recent major review paper highlighted a series of topics of contemporary significance that would be promising trajectories for bioarchaeological research (Buikstra et al., 2022). These topics include ethics, social inequality, identity (including intersectionality), climate change, migration, violence, epidemic disease, adaptability/plasticity, the osteological paradox, and the developmental origins of health and disease. While all these themes are highly relevant in most parts of the world, including the EMME, we felt that, among them, climate change, migration, violence and intersectionality are particularly relevant in the EMME region; hence they form the focus of this section. More specifically, the EMME is at high risk of becoming a climate change hotspot, with the region warming up almost twice as fast compared to the global average (Zittis et al., 2022). Regarding migration, according to a report by the UN Refugee Agency, in 2022 there were 3.6 million Syrians under temporary protection in Turkey, and another 22,730 displaced individuals arrived in Europe through the Eastern Mediterranean route (<https://data.unhcr.org/en/documents/details/98768>; accessed 17/02/2023). Finally, the tumultuous political history of the region, marked by repeated and ongoing war-

fare and other forms of conflict (Axt, 2022), has resulted in elevated violence; both in the form of direct violence and in terms of oppression, with women, children, and other vulnerable groups suffering disproportionately (structural violence and intersectionality). This section of the paper explores the extent to which bioarchaeological research has been used to shed light on the diachronic character of these topics, which reflect pressing contemporary issues affecting the economic, social, and political structure of the EMME region.

3.1. Intersectionality

Intersectionality refers to the fact that all individuals have multiple identities (e.g., gender, age, social status, ethnicity) that intersect and shape us as *Homo sapiens*. The intersectionality approach explores social relations by examining intersecting forms of discrimination; it acknowledges that social systems are complex and many forms of oppression (e.g. racism, sexism, ageism), may be present in a person's life simultaneously and interact interchangeably (Crenshaw, 1989). Therefore, intersectionality is a necessary framework when engaging with issues of privilege and power. Intersectionality has recently started being embedded in bioarchaeological interpretations. In his study of industrial-era skeletal assemblages from England, Yaussy (2019) assessed the intersecting axes of privilege, marginalization, and structural oppression by highlighting how high-status females were often impervious to negative health outcomes, while low-class males were susceptible to injury and disease. Intersectional facets can be also attested in other studies from North America and the United Kingdom (Byrnes, 2017; Knudson et al., 2020; Mant et al., 2021).

Because it represents socioeconomic structures that conceal multiple subregional, national, and subnational disparities, the EMME is a prime region in which to employ intersectional bioarchaeological research. Social disparities and inequalities are intertwined with the region's rooted religious and ethnic affiliations and divides, as many sectarian groups are divided across several states and maintain different power positions depending on the geographical area they are in (Mahmood, 2015; Makdisi, 2000). This exacerbates the region's inequality-related challenges, which has been characterized by ongoing conflicts, mass migration, governance and institutional deficits, and unstable economic development (Arghyrou, 2015; Guechati and Chami, 2022; Haas, 2005; Hammond, 2015; Vatikiotis, 2016). Finally, an important dimension of intersecting social norms and power structures are gender-based inequalities (Al-Shami, 2021; Nazir, 2005).

Bioarchaeological studies from the EMME region have yet to integrate the theory of intersectionality explicitly in their framework, with the only important exception being the work of Sulosky Weaver (2022) on marginalised (in terms of disability, socioeconomic status, ancestry and ethnicity) groups in the ancient Greek world, which argues that intersectionality promoted social marginalisation in the Late Archaic/Classical Greek world. Nonetheless, several bioarchaeological studies in the EMME have explored issues of health, dietary and other forms of inequality, both between genders (or rather biological sexes) and other social groups to examine different expressions of hierarchy (see contributions in Lagia and Voutsaki, in press; Schepartz et al., 2017). In the future, it is essential to embed such studies more explicitly in the analytical framework of intersectionality since the EMME region was at the crossroads of civilizations with highly diverse social structures and divisions; hence, following the intersectionality approach will allow a better understanding of past identities, in addition to elucidating the structures that instigated and reinforced inequalities in the past.

3.2. Climate change

The EMME region has a radius of 2,000 kilometers. Industrialization, population growth, and land conversion have resulted in this region becoming a climate change 'hotspot' (Lelieveld et al., 2012). The climate has undergone substantial changes in the last decade, with significantly dryer and warmer conditions emerging, while future projections are even more grim. The mean temperature is expected to rise by 3-5 degrees Celsius by mid-century, a decrease in rain fall is expected to result in river discharge decrease of 10-30% by the end of the 21st century, while extended heat waves, and increase in ozone smog and fine aerosol particles are also foreseen (Lelieveld et al., 2016; Shaheen et al., 2021). The milder winters and hotter summers are expected to alter EMME's biodiversity in fauna and flora, as well as promote an increase in invasive species (Bardsley and Edwards-Jones, 2007; Gordo and Sanz, 2010).

Bioarchaeology can offer a deeper understanding of the ways in which past societies adapted to climate change under different circumstances (Robbins Schug, 2020). It has a key role in understanding diverse stressors (e.g. diseases, dietary inefficiencies) and biocultural identities (e.g. social status, kinship), which are crucial in exploring aspects of human resilience to environmental stressors (Buikstra et al., 2022). Climate change has been studied systematically through bioarchaeology in recent years to test the degree of resilience of past communities across different temporal and spatial scales (mostly in North

America, mainland Europe and south Asia) (Hegmon et al., 2008; Nelson et al., 2006; Robbins Schug, 2011; Stojanowski, 2019; Tung et al., 2016).

Although the EMME is a 'hotspot' for climate change, few studies have addressed this topic in the framework of bioarchaeology. For example, Gregoricka (2016) examined changing climatic patterns at the Bronze Age sites of Umm an-Nar and Wad Suq in the Arabian Peninsula using stable oxygen isotope ratios. The isotopic data revealed homogeneous signatures indicative of continuity, elucidating the successful adaptability of local communities to changing environments and preservation of their way of life. In contrast, the adaptive response of Syrian Neolithic communities to climate instability and the transition from rain-fed agriculture to marginal environments involved the introduction of neurotoxic grass peas (*Lathyrus sativus*) into their diet, posing risks to human health (Merrett and Meiklejohn, 2015). The above studies showcase the potential of bioarchaeology to shed light to the diverse responses of past societies to climate change and their implications for the short- and long-term sustainability of these societies. Much more research in this direction is necessary so that climate change adaptation can be elucidated with higher spatial and temporal resolution.

3.3. Violence

Galtung (1990) identified three interconnected dimensions of violence: direct, structural, and cultural. *Direct violence* threatens one's life and/or inhibits an individual from meeting basic human needs. *Structural violence* refers to the systematic and unjust means by which some marginalized groups are denied opportunities to access goods and services that enable them to fulfil their basic human needs (Vorobej, 2008). Finally, *cultural violence* reflects social beliefs that normalize direct and structural violence (Burton, 1997).

Direct violence has been extensively studied in bioarchaeological research through the recording of skeletal trauma resulting from inter-personal aggression (Judd and Roberts, 1998, 1999; Lebedev et al., 2018; Milner et al., 2008; Osterholtz et al., 2019). More recently, structural and cultural violence have also started being critically examined, for instance in the context of health disparities affecting vulnerable or marginalized segments of past communities (e.g. females or individuals of the lower social strata) (Tremblay and Reedy, 2020).

Violence is a well-addressed topic in bioarchaeological research throughout the EMME region, with studies often tackling aspects of past violence in tandem with other variables such as gender-divisions (Monge and Selinsky, 2019), climate change (Florenova et al., 2020), migration (Osterholtz, 2017), and social stratification (Glencross and Knüsel, 2015;

Knüsel et al., 2018; Lorentz and Casa, 2020). As described above, structural violence is more than just physical trauma; it also encompasses embodied sociopolitical power dynamics and inherent inequalities. Therefore, aside from skeletal trauma, the effects of structural violence can manifest as skeletal 'nonspecific stress markers' (Tuchscherer, 2019), nutritional deficiencies (Pitre et al., 2016), infectious diseases, and mechanical strain (Kyle et al., 2016), all of which are aspects that have been examined in the EMME, though not explicitly linked with structural violence. Another aspect of structural violence in bioarchaeology relates to the postmortem treatment of the body. Studies from the EMME have explored the mistreatment, neglect, or destruction of skeletal remains based on past notions of conflict (Weerasinghe, 2020), though again not explicitly linking these phenomena to structural violence. In the future, we foresee more publications explicitly discussing aspects of structural violence, potentially in conjunction with intersectionality.

3.4. Migration

Throughout time, large segments of the human populace were actively mobile. This mobility took diverse forms (e.g. long- or short-distance, temporary or permanent) and had diverse motivations (e.g. slavery, intermarriage, military service, trade) (Pitoski et al., 2021). The impact of mobility throughout history has been variable and dependent on its character and context. Looking at recent data, in 2015, more than one million asylum seekers arrived to Europe by sea (Achilli, 2015). The majority of the asylum seekers were housed in rural communities and small towns that had not previously experienced large-scale immigration (Rudolph and Wagner, 2022) and certain political parties stressed that asylum seekers posed a threat to European identity, national security, and social and cultural homogeneity (Paluck et al., 2019). These pressing issues, however, do not constitute an exclusively modern phenomenon. Bioarchaeology is ideally placed to explore past mobility at different scales (from the individual to the population), but also assess the impact of mobility on health and disease, diet, violence, and other aspects of the lifeway of past people (Dahlstedt et al., 2021; Diaz-del-Rio et al., 2022; Stantis et al., 2022).

Palaeomobility studies from the EMME region are highly relevant in bioarchaeological research, covering themes of social/ethnic identities (Somel et al., 2016, Stantis et al., 2020), kinship/biological-relatedness (Gregoricka and Sheridan, 2017), admixture (Harber et al., 2018), forced migration/enslavement (Matisoo-Smith et al., 2018), disease transmission (Donoghue et al., 2015), and climate change (Benz et

al., 2016). Although more research is required to refine understanding of past mobility across time and space in the EMME, existing studies highlight the complexity of human movement and its impacts, and contradict deterministic modern political rhetoric that stresses the deleterious impact of human migration.

4. SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

Bioarchaeology of the EMME has largely kept pace with methodological and conceptual developments in Western Europe and North America, and it has made substantial contributions to the understanding of life in past human communities, elucidating aspects of activity, demography, diet, disease, mobility, kinship and others. Several studies in the EMME have addressed pressing issues of the past with contemporary implications (e.g. climate change, violence, migration) as well as adopted explicitly or implicitly theoretical approaches that acknowledge the complexity of past identities (e.g. intersectionality).

As briefly presented above, the intersectionality approach focuses on intersecting forms of discrimination and oppression, and it has recently started being explicitly adopted in bioarchaeological studies on privilege and marginalization across the world. The EMME, a region characterised by social inequalities rooted in religious, ethnic, economic, and other divides, is a prime area for the application of the intersectionality approach in bioarchaeological research with the aim of offering a deeper time perspective on these issues. Several bioarchaeological studies in the EMME have explored issues of inequality; however, we could only find a single study that explicitly framed this research in the context of intersectionality; stressing the great potential of this approach and

the need for further emphasis in this direction. In terms of climate, the EMME region is considered a climate change 'hotspot'. Bioarchaeological research has elucidated the adaptive responses of different groups in the region to climate instability, highlighting diverse strategies for sustainability and the need to move beyond deterministic scenarios that support that mass migrations, violence and instability are a one-way response to climate change. Regarding violence, direct inter-personal violence has been systematically studied in the EMME, often in association to climate change, migration, gender or other social divisions. In contrast, structural violence, which expresses socio-political power dynamics and inequalities, has been examined in terms of differential susceptibility to physiological stress, nutritional deficiencies, infectious diseases, and mechanical strain, as well as with regard to the mistreatment of the dead, though relevant research was not explicitly linked with structural violence. Contrary to the above themes, mobility (in the form of migration and other types of movement) has been systematically examined in the EMME, stressing its complex character and motivations in different contexts across time and space.

Existing studies exemplify how much can be achieved in the region and show the potential of adopting in bioarchaeology rigorous multi-scalar techniques that approach important questions about past human life that are relevant to modern society. More systematic research is required, developed taking into consideration the above matters from its inception stage, and current trends in published studies support that indeed such research is under way.

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